

Legal aspects of the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions and removals from land use, land use change and forestry in the scope of the climate and energy framework*

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Abstract

The aim of the paper is an attempt to assess whether the current legal regulations can be perceived as conducive to achievement of the Energy Union targets in terms of forest management? In particular, can the solutions that Poland adopted in the National Forestry Accounting Plan be assessed as conducive to achievement of the LULUCF Regulation's assumptions. The mechanisms of CO₂ emission and removal accounting are based on historical data in assumption and they are to aim at the effects anticipated for the future. While examining regulations, it is impossible to decide a priori whether the regulation in question will bring anticipated effects or losses from the economic perspective in terms of wood harvesting from state forests. It will depend on the result of emission and removal accounting.

Ziel des Aufsatzes ist es zu beurteilen, ob die derzeitigen gesetzlichen Regelungen für die Erreichung der Ziele der Energieunion in Bezug auf die Waldbewirtschaftung förderlich sind. Insbesondere, ob die Lösungsansätze, die Polen mit dem "National Forestry Accounting Plan" verabschiedet hat, als geeignet für das Erreichen der Voraussetzungen der LULUCF-Verordnung bewertet werden können. Die Mechanismen der Bilanzierung von CO₂-Emissionen und -abbau basieren auf historischen Daten und sollen für die Zukunft erwartete Effekte erzielen. Es ist unmöglich im Voraus zu beurteilen, ob die fragliche Verordnung aus wirtschaftlicher Sicht im Hinblick auf die Holzernte aus Staatswäldern erwartete Auswirkungen oder Verluste bringen wird. Dies wird vom Ergebnis der Bilanzierung von Emissionen und Abbau abhängen.

1. Introduction

This paper considers legal aspects of the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions and removals resulting from land use, land use change and forestry in the scope of the climate and energy framework.¹ The issue presented in the title of this paper regards, in general, the problem of climate protection which is included in the regulation regarding 'the governance of the Energy Union'. According to Regulation (EU) 2018/1999, the Energy Union should cover five dimensions: energy security, the internal energy market, energy efficiency, decarbonisation and research, innovation and

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¹ Cf. Forest governance and climate-change mitigation, Published by FAO and ITTO 2009, <http://www.fao.org/forestry/19488-0a2b1be34bcc2f24f780036ed0c5f9d69.pdf>, [access: 21 Sept 2018].

competitiveness.² The goal of the Energy Union in terms of climate is to give Union consumers, including households and businesses, secure, sustainable, competitive and affordable energy, and to foster research and innovation, which requires preservation, protection and improvement of the quality of the environment as well as support for rational natural resources' use. The priority of the governance of the Energy Union, in turn, should be to enable achievement of the Union's goals, especially 2030 climate and energy framework in terms of reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, renewable energy and energy efficiency.³ Thus, the above-mentioned regulation is related to climate change mitigation on a global scale.

The climate and energy framework includes the issues of greenhouse gas emissions and removals related to lands that have been sorted out by Regulation (EU) 2018/841 which is referred to as LULUCF⁴ as well as the Effort Sharing Regulation⁵ (referred to as ESR) which establishes binding annual greenhouse gas emission targets for Member States in 2021 – 2030. The LULUCF Regulation includes the European Union's commitment to achieve net-zero emissions in the sector under this regulation in 2012 – 2030. This law regards all developed lands, including forests, agricultural land, grassland and (by 2026) wetland and it establishes a new EU management process for the purpose of monitoring of Member States' calculations of removals and emissions from forestry.

² Art. 1 sec. 2 of Regulation (EU) 2018/1999 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 on the Governance of the Energy Union and Climate Action, amending Regulations (EC) 663/2009 and (EC) 715/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council, Directives 94/22/EC, 98/70/EC, 2009/31/EC, 2009/73/EC, 2010/31/EU, 2012/27/EU and 2013/30/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, Council Directives 2009/119/EC and (EU) 2015/652 and repealing Regulation (EU) No 525/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council (OJL328/1, p. 1 of 21 December 2018), hereinafter referred to as Regulation 2018/1999.

³ Points 2, 3 and 18 of the preamble to Regulation 2018/1999.

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2018/841 of the European Parliament and of the Council on the inclusion of greenhouse gas emissions and removals from land use, land use change and forestry in the 2030 climate and energy framework, and amending Regulation (EU) 525/2013 and Decision 529/2013/EU (OJ L 156 of 19 June 2018, p. 1), hereinafter referred to as Regulation 2018/841 or LULUCF Regulation (from 'land use, land use change and forestry'); cf. N. Forsell, A. Korosuo, S. Federici, M. Gusti, J-J Rincón-Cristóbal, S. Rüter, B. Sánchez-Jiménez, C. Dore , O. Brajterman, J. Gardiner, *Guidance on developing and reporting the Forest Reference Levels in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2018/841*. Available online at: https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/forests/lulucf_en, [dostęp: 15.9.2019]; H. Böttcher, C. Zell-Ziegler, A. Herold, A. Siemons, *EU LULUCF Regulation explained Summary of core provisions and expected effects*, Berlin, 21.06.2019, <https://www.oeko.de/fileadmin/oekodoc/Analysis-of-LULUCF-Regulation.pdf>, [access: 20 Sept 2019].

⁵ Regulation (EU) 2018/842 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 on binding annual greenhouse gas emission reductions by Member States from 2021 to 2030 contributing to climate action to meet commitments under the Paris Agreement, and amending Regulation (EU) 525/2013 (OJ L 156 of 19 June 2018, p. 26), hereinafter referred to as Regulation 2018/842.

The topic of this paper has not been discussed in legal literature so far. Some issues related to climate protection have been raised in textbooks, foreign publications⁶ and literature on forestry⁷.

The insufficient level of research provokes cognitive needs which justify consideration of the topic in question. Another factor that supports this research are social and economic issues resulting from the need to protect the climate. The urgency to consider this topic is confirmed by most recent results of analyses of the environment's condition presented e.g. in the sixth *Global Environment Outlook*⁸ report which was published in March 2019. It includes detailed information on the condition of the environment. The motto of the report is 'Healthy planet, healthy people' and it points to climate change, air pollution, urbanization, food waste and natural resource waste, soil degradation and biodiversity deficiency as the main threats.

According to the UNEP Emissions Gap Report of 2017⁹, G-20 countries (which generate around three fourth of global greenhouse gas emissions) can undertake commitments together. It is estimated that the European Union should be able to fulfil its commitments without any international compensation, like China, India and Japan. Australia, Brazil and Russia should also be able to fulfil their commitments.¹⁰ The intensity of greenhouse gas emissions in the EU, reflected in GDP, will probably remain the lowest in the G-20 by 2030.¹¹ However, maintaining of the global warming level much below 2°C (or 1.5°C) requires faster decarbonisation in countries which have big, strong economies with constantly growing level of greenhouse gas emissions.

⁶ Cf. M. Górski (ed.), *Prawo ochrony środowiska*, Warszawa 2018, pp. 290 – 293. A. Bolte, *Adaptive forest management in central Europe: Climate change impacts, strategies and integrative concept*, Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research 2009, Vol. 24, Issue 6, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02827580903418224>, access: 1 Oct 2017; M. Lindner, T. Suominen, *Towards a sustainable bioeconomy*, Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research 2017, vol. 32(7), pp. 549-550, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02827581.2017.1288826>, access: 1 Oct 2017; L. Palloni, *Il ruolo delle foreste nella lotta al global warming e la sostenibilità ambientale: il caso del Canada*, w: Studi in onore di Luigi Costato volume primo. Diritto Agrario e Agroambientale, Napoli 2014, pp. 463-574; National Forest Program. Synthesis, programs, introductions, overviews and recommendations of eight expert panels: climate, value, heritage, protection, development, organization, cooperation, science, Sękocin Stary, 18 June 2013 – 8 December 2015, ed. K. Rykowski, Instytut Badawczy Leśnictwa 2016, p. 170, <http://www.npl.ibles.pl/sites/default/files/synteza.pdf>, [access: 14 Jul 2017].

⁷ Cf. A. Kaliszewski, *Cele polityki leśnej w Polsce w świetle aktualnych priorytetów leśnictwa w Europie Część 1. Procesy kształtujące politykę leśną w Europie*, Leśne Prace Badawcze, Marzec / March 2018, Vol. 79 (1): 77–87, PDF version: www.lesne-prace-badawcze.pl; DOI: 10.2478/frp-2018-0009.

⁸ Report prepared at the initiative of the *United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP)* and published during UN Environment Assembly in Nairobi (Kenya), <https://www.unenvironment.org/resources/global-environment-outlook-6>, access: 30 August 2019.

⁹ <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/22070>, [access: 10 Jun 2019].

¹⁰ *Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the EU Council and the Paris Climate Agreement: Taking stock of progress at Katowice COP (required under Article 21 of Regulation (EU) 525/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2013 on the mechanisms for monitoring and reporting greenhouse gas emissions and for reporting other information at national and Union level relevant to climate change and repealing Decision No 280/2004/EC)*, {SWD (2018) 453 final}, Brussels, 26 October 2018, COM(2018)716 final, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0716>, [access: 10 Jun 2019].

¹¹ *The Emissions Gap Report 2016: A UNEP Synthesis Report*: <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/unep/document/emissions-gap-report-2016-unep-synthesis-report>, [access: 10 June 2019].

The EU has established 2050 emission reduction targets and they are included in the 2020 climate and energy package and the 2030 climate and energy framework. They assume a shift to zero emissions economy by 2050. The 2020 package is a collection of binding regulations which are to guarantee that the EU will achieve its targets in terms of climate and energy by 2020. Among these targets there are: reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by 20 percent (in comparison with 1990), 20-percent share of renewable energy in total energy consumption in the EU and increase of energy efficiency by 20 percent. Achievement of these targets will proceed in a few areas.

When it comes to achievement of targets so far, in 2017 the level of emissions in the majority of Member States was lower than their annual emissions limits. Nine countries (Greece, Slovakia, Croatia, Romania, Hungary, Portugal, Sweden, the Netherlands and Slovenia) had emissions at least 10 p.p. lower than the limit.¹² Malta, Germany, Ireland, Austria, Cyprus, Poland and Finland, on the other hand, exceeded their annual limits – according to estimates – just as Bulgaria, Estonia and Lithuania did, but by less than 1p.p.¹³

In terms of forecasts for the future, it is indicated that countries such as Estonia, Latvia, Finland, Germany, Lithuania, Austria, Romania, Poland and Spain, assuming that they will continue the current strategies, will be over 10 p.p. short of achieving 2030 targets. All Member States that anticipate they may not be able to achieve 2030 targets should specify in their national climate and energy plans (on the basis of the Energy Union governance regulation) how they would try to fulfil their commitments. So it is important how Member States, including Poland, will aim at fulfilling their ‘climate’ commitments.

Keeping the above-mentioned commitments of Member States in mind, it is justified to define the goal of the considerations which sounds as follows: the goal of this paper is an attempt to assess whether the current legal regulations can be perceived as conducive to achievement of the Energy Union targets in terms of forest management? In particular, can the solutions that Poland adopted in the National Forestry Accounting Plan¹⁴ be assessed as conducive to achievement of the LULUCF Regulation’s assumptions. Achievement of the target requires a closer look at the LULUCF as well as the national climate and energy plan and the national forestry accounting plan. Due to the size of the article, it is possible to only signal some issues and that is why the considerations do not exhaust the topic.

¹² Percentage points represent the difference between the volume of emissions and annual emission limit expressed as the percentage change in comparison with emissions in the base year 2005.

¹³ Report from the Commission to the European Parliament and the EU Council and the Paris Climate Agreement: Taking stock of progress at Katowice COP (required under Article 21 of Regulation (EU) 525/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 May 2013 on a mechanism for monitoring and reporting greenhouse gas emissions and for reporting other information at national and Union level relevant to climate change and repealing Decision No 280/2004/EC), {SWD (2018) 453 final}, Brussels, 26 October 2018, COM(2018)716 final, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52018DC0716>, [access: 10 Jun 2019].

¹⁴ National Forestry Accounting Plan developed by the Team for the elaboration of national plans related to accounting for greenhouse gas emissions and removals resulting from forestry activities, Warsaw 2018 https://bip.mos.gov.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/bip/strategie_plany_programy/Krajowy_Plan_Rozliczen_dla_Le_snictwa/NFAP_2018_POLAND_ENG_FINAL.pdf, p. 13, hereinafter referred to as NFAP.

2. The EU legal framework.

At the EU level, the protection and improvement of the environment falls under art. 11 or art. 191 of the TFEU.¹⁵ Achievement of the adopted targets is related to Member States' commitment to develop integrated national energy and climate plans that should be consistent with the UN's sustainable development goals. The point is to achieve the goal in the form of maintaining world's average temperature growth much below 2°C in comparison with the level from before the industrial era and to try to limit this growth to 1.5°C above the level from before the industrial era as well as achieve long-term greenhouse gas emission reduction and larger removal by sinks in all sectors, in line with the EU target.¹⁶ As it is commonly known, the main anthropogenic factor behind global warming is the accumulation of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere.

Processes of greenhouse gas removal are referred to as 'sinks' and processes of greenhouse gas emission, such as fuel combustion – as 'sources'. According to the LULUCF Regulation (art. 3 sec. 1 points 1, 2, 3), a 'sink' is any process, activity or mechanism that removes a greenhouse gas, an aerosol or a precursor to a greenhouse gas from the atmosphere. A 'source' is any process, activity or mechanism that releases a greenhouse gas, an aerosol or a precursor to a greenhouse gas into the atmosphere. A 'carbon pool' is the whole or part of a biogeochemical feature or system within the territory of a Member State and within which carbon, any precursor to a greenhouse gas containing carbon or any greenhouse gas containing carbon is stored. The most important sinks are oceans and land biomass. The sum of sources and sinks gives the net emission result. The main anthropogenic greenhouse gases include: carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O). The LULUCF Regulation lists all greenhouse gases as the CO₂ equivalent (influence of the CO₂ equivalent mass in the atmosphere on radiative forcing).¹⁷ In the LULUCF sector, the biggest sink are forests and the estimated CO₂ removal volume is generated primarily by live biomass growth.¹⁸ That is why it is justified to say that legal regulations regarding forest share in climate protection may be significant for the achievement of EU targets.

As it has been mentioned, the climate and energy framework includes the sector of land use, land use change and forestry. On the one hand, it is exposed to the effects of climate change and on the other, it may contribute to mitigation of this change. In the case of EU lands, removals are bigger than emissions and the LULUCF Regulation focuses on development of incentives to at least maintain this situation. In the light of this regulation, every Member State has to make sure that greenhouse gas emissions from land use are completely balanced with CO₂ removal from the atmosphere through activity in this sector. This process is subject to the 'zero balance' principle, according to which it is necessary to compensate for emissions generated by deforestation with e.g. provision of equivalent CO₂ sinks from afforestation or improvement of sustainable management of existing forests.

¹⁵ The Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, OJ C 326, no 90, item 864/2.

¹⁶ Points 36 and 37 of the preamble to Regulation (EU) 2018/2019.

¹⁷ National Forestry Accounting Plan developed by the Team for the elaboration of national plans related to accounting for greenhouse gas emissions and removals resulting from forestry activities, Warsaw 2018, p. https://bip.mos.gov.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/bip/strategie_plany_programy/Krajowy_Plan_Rozliczen_dla_Le_snictwa/NFAP_2018_POLAND_ENG_FINAL.pdf, p. 13, hereinafter referred to as NFAP.

¹⁸ Ibidem, p. 14.

The most important commitment of Member States under the LULUCF Regulation (art. 4) is for each of them to ensure that for the periods from 2021 to 2025 and from 2026 to 2030, taking into account the flexibilities provided for in art. 12 and 13, emissions do not exceed removals (calculated as the sum of total emissions and total removals on its territory in all of the land accounting categories, as accounted in accordance with this regulation). In these accounts emissions should be denoted by a positive sign (+) and removals – by a negative sign (–). Besides, every Member State is obliged to maintain accounts that accurately reflect the emissions and removals resulting from the land accounting categories included in the above-mentioned regulations. In his respect they also have to ensure accuracy, completeness, consistency, comparativeness and transparency of their accounts and other data provided under the regulations (art. 5 of the LULUCF Regulation). An important rule regarding the accounts is the requirement to avoid double counting of emissions or removals, in particular by ensuring that emissions and removals are not accounted for under more than one land accounting category (art. 5 sec. 2 of the LULUCF Regulation).

When it comes to afforested and deforested land, emissions and removals should be accounted as the total emissions and total removals for each year in the periods from 2021 to 2025 and from 2026 to 2030 (art. 6 sec. 1 of the LULUCF Regulation). Every Member State should also account for emissions and removals resulting from managed forest land, calculated as emissions and removals in the periods from 2021 to 2025 and from 2026 to 2030 minus the value obtained by multiplying by five the forest reference level of the Member State concerned (art. 8 sec. 1 of the LULUCF Regulation). However, if the result is negative with reference to the forest reference level¹⁹ of a given Member State, the Member State concerned shall include in its managed forest land accounts ‘total net removals of no more than the equivalent of 3.5 percent of the emissions of that Member State in its base year or period, as specified in Annex III, multiplied by five’. There is an exception specified in the LULUCF Regulation (net removals from the carbon pools of dead wood and harvested wood products, except the category of paper as referred to in art. 9 sec. 1 point a), in the land accounting category of managed forest land.

The reference level for lands must be based on the continuation of sustainable forest management practice documented from 2000 to 2009 with reference to dynamic age-related forest characteristics in national forests with the use of the best available data. This level shall also take into consideration ‘the future impact of dynamic age-related forest characteristics in order not to unduly constrain forest management intensity as a core element of sustainable forest management practice, with the aim of maintaining or strengthening long-term carbon sinks’ (art.8 sec. 5 of the LULUCF Regulation).

However, there is a possibility to apply ‘flexibilities’ (art. 12 and 13 of the LULUCF Regulation). In particular, if a Member State exhibits net removals from land use and forestry, it can hand over these amounts to other Member States. Similarly, Member States can compensate for shortages in the LULUCF sector, using annual emission limits granted under Regulation (EU) 2018/842. Varying ability to undertake action by Member States has been taken into consideration.

¹⁹ ‘Forest reference level’ is, according to art. 3 sec. 1 point 7 of the LULUCF Regulation, the estimated forest reference level expressed in tons of CO₂ equivalent per year, of the average annual net emissions or removals resulting from forest land management in a given Member State in the periods from 2021 to 2025 and from 2026 to 2030, based on the criteria established in this Regulation.

The LULUCF Regulation also assumes that the proportion of acquired wood used for harvested wood products and bioenergy from 2000 – 2009 shall be maintained. There is a mechanism of compensation for possible emission from managed forest land in case a given country does not achieve the removal volume equal to the reference level and its operation is based exclusively on the Member State's forest coverage (average forest coverage in the reference period from 2000 to 2009). Poland has been granted a compensation limit for 10 years (2021 – 2030) in the amount of -22.5 million tons of CO₂ equivalent as total maximum limit for this period. However, accounting of balances for afforestation or deforestation and harvested wood products (excluding paper) shall not be restricted with either a limit or a reference level.

3. National regulations

The sustainable development principle has been expressed in art. 5 of the Constitution of Poland²⁰. Under art. 74 of the Constitution of Poland, public authorities are obliged to run policy that guarantees ecological security to the contemporary and future generations and environmental protection is the obligation of public authorities. According to the art. 1 of the Forest Act, this law regulates 'the rules of behavior, protection and expansion of forest resources and the rules of forest management in relation to other elements of the environment and the national economy'.²¹ In the light of provisions of the above-mentioned Act, forest management should be consistent with the rules of common forest protection, durability of their maintenance, continuity and sustainable use of all forest functions as well as increase of forest resources and rules specified in the Act on maintaining the national character of natural resources which imposes the obligation to manage resources 'according to the rule of sustainable development in the public interest'.

Legal definition of 'permanently sustainable forestry'²² also refers to the above-mentioned rule. It is defined as 'activity that aims at developing forest structure and use in such a manner and rate that will guarantee permanent preservation of their biological richness, high productivity and regeneration potential, life and ability to fulfil, now and in the future, of all important protective, economic and social functions at the local, national and global level, without damage to other ecosystems'. It seems that the legislator's intention was to prioritize the protective functions of forests.²³ The literature states that protective functions of forests are expressed in, among other things, 'positive influence of forests on development of global and local climate, composition of the atmosphere, regulation of water circulation, prevention of floods, avalanches and landslide, protection of soil from erosion and protection of landscape from steppe-formation, preservation of biological potential of a big number

²⁰ Constitution of the Republic of Poland of 2 April 1997, Journal of Laws, item 483, as amended, hereinafter referred to as the Constitution of Poland.

²¹ Art. 1 point 1 of the Forest Act of 28 September 1991, Journal of Laws of 2018, item 2129, as amended, hereinafter referred to as the Forest Act.

²² Art. 6 sec. 1 point 1a of the Forest Act; cf. United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change produced in New York on 9 May 1992, ratified by Poland through an act of 16 June 1994, Journal of Laws of 1994, no 53, item 1238.

²³ Cf. K. Leśkiewicz, *Prawne aspekty zarządzania lasami Skarbu Państwa*, Lublin 2019, p. 86 and 92.

of species and ecosystems as well as landscape diversity and better conditions for agricultural production'.²⁴

It means that in the light of the Forest Act, climate protection can and should be pursued within protective functions. However, the Act misses more specific requirements regarding implementation of protective functions in terms of climate protection. Such solutions have been developed within documents required under Regulation (EU) 2018/841 as well as in practice. According to the LULUCF Regulation, Member States are obliged to submit the national forestry accounting plan to the European Commission, including proposed forest reference level, by 31 December 2018 for the period from 2021 to 2025 and by 30 June 2023 for the period from 2026 to 2030 (art. 8 sec. 3 of the LULUCF Regulation). After Member States submit these plans, the Commission, in consultation with experts appointed by the Member States, will conduct a 'technical assessment', including verification, of the extent to which the proposed forest reference levels have been established in accordance with the requirements of the LULUCF Regulation (art.8 sec. 6 of the LULUCF Regulation).

Poland has adopted the draft of National Energy and Climate Plan for 2021-2030²⁵, in which it declares to use the flexibilities of the Effort Sharing Regulation²⁶, especially the mechanism specified in art. 7 of the LULUCF Regulation as well as an additional pool of units that expand the annual limit (art. 10 sec. 2) and the mechanism of shifting, borrowing and transferring of AEA units (art. 5). The document states that Member States can shift the unused portion of their limits to subsequent years of the accounting period, borrow a portion of their limits from future years or acquire units from other Member States. Poland also assumes that it will use the security reserve (art. 11) in case other flexibilities turned out to be insufficient to cover AEA shortage in 2026 – 2030. The maximum total pool for all Member States that will fulfill the specific conditions amounts to 105 million tons of CO₂ equivalent. The National Energy and Climate Plan assumes using of all available additional mechanisms that allow to mitigate the effects of the ambitious EU targets, but it does not cover the most important issues. The European Commission believes that the plan does not include means to solve the problem of anticipated significant difference in relation to the 2030 target that assumes greenhouse gas emissions of -7 percent in Poland in comparison with 2005 in sectors that are not included in the EU system of emission trading.²⁷

Moreover, the most important challenge for forestry is implementation of such actions that will enable increase of carbon retention capacity in the elements of forest ecosystem. In particular, it is assumed that the use of wood regulated by forest use management is the effect of needs resulting

²⁴ P. Paschalis-Jakubowicz, *Polskie leśnictwo w Unii Europejskiej*, Warszawa 2004, p. 147.

²⁵ Draft of National Energy and Climate Plan for 2021-2030. Objectives and targets, and policies and measures. Version 3.1 of 4 January 2019 <https://www.gov.pl/attachment/33ddfff1-fd75-4070-85e9-98b254420058>, access: 9 Sept 2019; cf. Energy Policy of Poland, and Strategy for Responsible Development by 2020 – with the perspective by 2030 of 2017.

²⁶ *Ibidem*, p. 53.

²⁷ Cf. Commission Recommendation of 18 June 2019 on the draft integrated National Energy and Climate Plan of Poland covering the period from 2021 to 2030 (2019/C 297/21), OJ C of 3 September 2019. Point 1 of the above-mentioned recommendation orders submission of additional information on the planned policies and measures whose goal is to solve the problem in question. It refers to e.g. specification of information on additional measures, especially in construction sector, agriculture and land use, land use change and forestry as well as application of accounting rules established in Regulation 2018/841.

from forest growing and protective functions and is supposed to guarantee continuity of production of as much top quality wood as possible. The volume of wood harvesting from mature forests should take into account the limitations resulting from implementation of protective and social functions, the condition of current and future structure of forest age and species and the degree of its compatibility with the habitat characteristics.²⁸

In this respect, it is necessary to reach to Poland's National Forestry Accounting Plan²⁹, which – for the purpose of achievement of national targets specified in the LULUCF Regulation – divides forests on the basis of the structure of use, intensity of main use as well as availability and credibility of data regarding condition of forests and forestry, into two stratification layers: state-owned forests managed by the State Forests National Forest Holding (hereinafter referred to as SF NFH) – around 77 percent of forests – and forests outside of the SF NFH authority (so-called 'other forests' that include forests of the remaining ownership forms, primarily privately-owned forests, forests managed by national parks and owned by the Agricultural Property Stock of the State Treasury, other forests of the Treasury and communal forests). In other forests the NFAP observes a different forestry method with lower primary use levels than in forests managed by SF NFH.³⁰

When it comes to wood harvesting in relation to the forest reference level, in the beginning of 2010 the share of harvesting in the logging use in forests managed by SF NFH amounted to ca 48 percent and in other forests – to ca 26 percent. According to available forecasts, this share may go up in subsequent periods – to ca 58 percent in state forests and 41 percent in other forests in the period from 2026 to 2030.³¹ Considering the current level that began in 2017, the share in logging use in forests managed by SF NFH amounted to ca 54 percent and in other forests – to ca 23 percent. According to available forecasts, this share may go up in subsequent periods – to ca 59 percent in state forests and ca 30 percent in other forests in 2026 – 2030.³²

Average estimated values of the annual balance of forest emissions and removals in the period from 2021 to 2025 for CRF 4.A.1 category 'Forest land remaining forest land', will amount to, considering a scenario based on the forest reference level, -33296 in 2021, -31229 in 2022, -29329 in 2023, -27595 in 2024 and -25717 in 2025. According to the base level, it gives -29433 tons of CO₂ equivalent per year (calculated according to the method adopted in section A of annex IV of Regulation (EU) 2018/841.³³ The National Forestry Accounting Plan also indicates that the area of forests according to the forest reference level in the entire period under analysis (2010 – 2030) will not change.

Another thing worth mentioning are actions undertaken by SF NFH regarding verification of the possibility to increase carbon retention capacity in state forests and other forests. It is an element of

²⁸ Ibidem, pp. 17-18.

²⁹ National Forestry Accounting Plan developed by the Team for the elaboration of national plans related to accounting for greenhouse gas emissions and removals resulting from forestry activities, Warsaw 2018, p. 16-17,
https://bip.mos.gov.pl/fileadmin/user_upload/bip/strategie_plany_programy/Krajowy_Plan_Rozliczen_dla_Leśnictwa/NFAP_2018_POLAND_ENG_FINAL.pdf, [access: 9 September 2019].

³⁰ NFAP, p. 6.

³¹ NFAP, p. 21.

³² NFAP, p. 23.

³³ NFAP, p. 45.

a long-term project entitled 'The Forest Carbon Farms' whose aim is to verify the possibilities of increased CO₂ removals by forests through additional economic and forestry actions.³⁴

Besides, we must keep in mind the role of forest biomass whose sources for energy purposes are: roundwood from forests and afforestation and byproducts from wood processing. Forest biomass accounts for around 20 percent of biomass used for energy purposes. In terms of accounting and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions from forest biomass used for energy purposes, the national plan of adaptation to climate change indicates that they are not included in accounting and reporting of the balance of emissions and removals within the forest land category. Emissions related to forest biomass used for energy purposes are reported and accounted as the effect of losses of forest biomass from forest land. It is also anticipated that bigger use of forest biomass by 2030 will have an influence on accounting and reporting of removals and emissions from forest land category, but currently this influence is yet to be determined.³⁵

At the same time, in the reference period (2000-2009), the forest management plan was governed by the rule that the sum of tasks within logging use and pre-logging use specified in the forest management plan is the maximum value. It meant that in case pre-logging use was increased, logging use had to be limited. Average logging age/rotation periods (in years) for the most important tree species in forests managed by SF NFH were as follows: pine – 106, spruce – 95, beech – 115, oak – 140, birch – 80, alder – 75. The NFAP emphasizes the difference between forests managed by SF NFH and forests under other ownership forms when it comes to planning and implementation of forest management plans.

In forests managed by SF NFH the volume of total primary use was in principle almost the same as the volume of planned primary use and in other forests, especially private ones, implementation of planned tasks was (like these days) much smaller. The methods of forest management were also different – in private forests management tends to be simplified and adjusted to their owners' needs 'within pre-logging use'. That is why in practice the majority of wood in private forests (around 80 percent) is harvested in 'pre-logging use' and around 20 percent – in 'logging use'.³⁶ It means that there is a need to improve legal regulations and practices regarding forest management in private forests.

4. Overview

Apparently, the mechanisms of accounting greenhouse gas emissions from land use in such a way that emissions are completely balanced with CO₂ removals from the atmosphere through forestry activity are very complex and have interdisciplinary character. They regard various areas, including forestry, economy or law. Thus, good knowledge and understanding of the rules they are subject to, requires confrontation of various viewpoints, which is impossible in such a short paper. The study shows that in order to examine possible effects of new legal solutions, their dogmatic analysis only is

³⁴ *Draft of National Energy and Climate Plan for 2021-2030. Objectives and targets, and policies and measures. Version 3.1 of 4 January 2019* <https://www.gov.pl/attachment/33ddfff1-fd75-4070-85e9-98b254420058>, [access: 9 September 2019], p. 55.

³⁵ *Ibidem*, p. 19.

³⁶ NFAP, p. 39.

not sufficient. Meanwhile, this is the only possible thing within the limited scope of this publication. It must be also noted that the assessment of economic effects of the LULUCF Regulation or the effects for forestry at the current stage of its implementation would be no more than a regular forecast.

However, from the legal viewpoint it is possible to conclude that LULUCF solutions have a significant influence on Member States' authority in terms of forestry, even though it is their responsibility under the decision of the European Court of Justice. They even develop common forestry policy in terms of climate, while the only thing Member States have left is the execution of assumed normative targets. In terms of analyzed emission and removal accounting mechanisms in forests, the LULUCF Regulation can be considered an act that rations forest use activity.

The mechanisms of CO₂ emission and removal accounting are based on historical data in assumption and they are to aim at the effects anticipated for the future. While examining regulations, it is impossible to decide a priori whether the regulation in question will bring anticipated effects or losses from the economic perspective in terms of wood harvesting from state forests. It will depend on the result of emission and removal accounting. If the level of permitted emissions of gases under the regulations is not exceeded, it does not have to mean that the volume of wood harvesting goes down and thus negative economic effects take place. The point is the amount of CO₂ emission in the process and whether it exceeds the established forest reference level. If emissions are higher than assumed, there is a possibility of compensation. After emission levels are exceeded despite using additional balance mechanisms, wood harvesting limits may be introduced. In the light of the LULUCF Regulation, the 'forest carbon farms' project can be assessed positively as so can be the planned afforestation of the country. The solutions and data adopted in the NFAP may indicate that the LULUCF Regulation does not have to be negative for Poland, although it is, indeed, very ambitious when it comes to the level of targets.

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